

D4.5 Möbius Book Final Prototype

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the final steps taken towards the implementation of the final prototype of the Möbius Book. This includes latest changes on both the creator and player. Furthermore, the report documents the user engagement activities that were done in task T4.3, the user feedback gathered and how it is integrated into the final prototype.

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Terminology and Acronyms

<i>EC</i>	<i>European Commission</i>
<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>FP</i>	<i>Framework Programme</i>
<i>PMB</i>	<i>Project Management Board</i>
<i>PMP</i>	<i>Project Management Plan</i>
<i>STAB</i>	<i>Scientific and Technical Advisory Board</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>DAW</i>	<i>Digital Audio Workstation</i>

1. Introduction

The Möbius Book consists of three major parts, the Möbius Creator's Toolkit, the Möbius Player, and the file format, which is an extension of the EPUB3 format. The Creator's Toolkit is built as a web-application and allows a user to assemble a Möbius book file, which can then be viewed with the Möbius Player. The Author creating a Möbius book can add several multimedia elements that can then be viewed by the reader based on their preferences. The mobile player prototype is a responsive application that allows users to fully experience the Möbius books and can be used on any device and operating system. If they have selected the 3D Audio version, once they open the book the voice narration SFX and Music will start playing creating a more immersive experience into the book's world. Multimedia elements can additionally be encountered and opened directly in the text of the book.

In this deliverable we show the final updates on the Möbius Creator's and Möbius Player prototypes taking into account the feedback from the users. The extension of the EPUB3 format has been implemented and reported in D4.3. Additionally, the user feedback studies will be presented in this deliverable and how the feedback was filtered and integrated into the development process.

2. User Feedback Integration

2.1. User engagement activities

To engage users of the tools and thus collect feedback, IMEC and DEN developed a methodology that could be used in pilot activities. This consisted of 2 procedures as a significant number of participants had to be reached in phase 3a, i.e., 530 for the Möbius Book. In the course of this phase of the project, the focus was put on a more qualitative way of collecting data as it had been found extremely difficult to reach people online via a quantitative survey. A distinction was made between the event-based testing procedure and the online testing procedure.

In the event-based procedure, the consortium partners attended an event (book fair or conference) and orally explained the application and afterwards asked for feedback on it. Feedback was generated through 2 types of questionnaires. For the general user evaluation survey¹, there were mainly open-ended questions. For example, in this questionnaire participants were asked about their first impression, likes, dislikes, potential, thresholds and what things they would change about the app. These questions provided an opportunity to engage in a structured conversation with the participant. The impact assessment survey focused more on the impact the tool had in different areas and contained specific scale questions. These evaluation questions came from surveys prepared in pilot phase 2 of the project. For the survey on the Creator², the questions were organized on adding/ creating 3D audio, books, chapters, media and included impact questions. The evaluation questions for the Player³ were divided into questions about consuming the book, features associated with owning a profile and impact questions. At an event, when possible, an email address of the

¹<https://forms.gle/bZ1d9RaM6hqNBKtv9>

²https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLScfEPTD6fMxmQV2IVM_E2YL3e7pt1YI8IkFcUgMyPONWsaIEw/viewform

³<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSex-vfD6TRreK1AgS9aHy9RulRxtfTa7-j3iX0XPpSRjkHxNg/viewform?vc=0&c=0&w=1&flr=0>

participant was also requested using an informed consent⁴. This was done with the intention of asking the participant for feedback at a later stage.

In the online testing procedure, a link to the Player and the Creator was shared widely via social media channels (LinkedIn, Twitter and Instagram) and email to call for testers. A plug-in survey app, Hotjar, allowed users to leave feedback for specific features and rate how satisfied they were with the application. These Hotjar questions were the same as the survey impact questions.

Book - This is a chapter page of a book in the Player. If the author created additional multimedia content for this chapter then you will see the Möbius logo below each paragraph where this content exists. Click there to enjoy this content!

You can disable hints by editing your profile preferences

Mehmet

The strait

Mehmet stood up and, with a deep breath, let his gaze wander above the strait. He looked at his right and saw the dark, vigorous Black Sea, immense in its unending power. All the copious amounts of water it received from the tributaries and the sky created the relentless tides of the Bosphorus. The waves, one after another, were almost fighting each other with all their strength on the surface of the canal, in a dance of confidence and arrogance. The evident coldness and saltiness of the water down there was invigorating the agitated, cruel currents. The waves were of a perfect Prussian blue, hazy and inconvertible; the nervous foam was insufferably rebelling against the Mistral winds, and each ancestral, earthly force was trying to prevail on the other.

The salty sea breeze was running through the cordage of the ships anchored to Saryyer harbour. Mehmet followed the coastline with his glance: after Fath Sultan Mehmet's bridge, broken like a defeated soldier, he was seeing dozens of old ottoman villas and elegant minarets, which graced the landscape with their beauty. He turned his gaze right in front of him. The elements that made him experience a bold sense of self just a couple of days before were standing right there: the terrace, his shadow and the calm gulfs which painted the water with all the shades of blue. The strait was calmer next to Küçüksu Palace, and the hills of Arnavutköy were partly dampening the big waves; it felt like the natural forces at play were resting, just for a bit, before clashing again.

The 3D audio helps me understand the story.

Feedback

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

Made with Hotjar

Next

Figure 1: Example of feedback request via Hotjar during interaction with the Player

In addition, (online) workshops were also held. This method allowed the applications to be explained more extensively and allowed participants during workshops for the Creator to work with their own data in the tool. For these (online) workshops, the general, open-ended questions were converted into a format that could be more interactive in a group setting. When the workshop was online, a digital collaboration platform, Miro, was used where participants could type their answers.

⁴<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLScWSAmdRPWawS9KT0S5mie9-0mzAjkqSVoMNBbzd5sGmE4lw/viewform>

Figure 2: Template in Miro used at an online workshop for the Creator

An informed consent⁵ was also always handed out during the (online) workshops to obtain consent for participation and use of data.

2.2. Feedback integration process

The feedback collected by these surveys were used to translate them into user requirements. All requirements were organized feature-by-feature in a user requirement document⁶ made by IMEC. For the Player, these were the following features: 3D audio integration, multimedia content, user experience, reading experience, additional content, evaluation on 3D audio

⁵<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLScWSAmdRPWawS9KTtoS5mie9-0mzAjkqSVoMNBbzd5sGmE4lw/viewform> & <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1JktxfaN1AGnlbjVkeFqkcXfmVwZgn8vFdHduQ6nNbLw/edit?usp=sharing>

⁶ [Overview user requirements.xlsx](#)

tracks and evaluation on mock-up. For the Creator, these were the following: evaluation on interface and structure of the application, creating books, 3D audio and evaluation on the Creator mock-up. The Moscow technique, which divides initiatives into four categories—must-have, should-have, could-have, and won't-have—was also used to rank these criteria. This made it clear to all partners whether and in what time frame the requirements would be integrated into the application. Throughout the project, these requirements were updated frequently.

Additionally, to pass on these user requirements and enhance the apps, IMEC maintained close contact with the other partners of the project through biweekly meetings. Receiving feedback and setting up requirements to pass it on to the technical partners was an iterative process. In addition, at this stage of the project, all partners were asked to go through the applications and share their issues and suggestions for improvement in the so-called Friendly User Test document⁷. Thus, the opportunity was taken to involve all partners in the feedback process and discover new insights from people within the project. Furthermore, all partners were asked to indicate after an event how many participants were reached with the surveys, via the Pilot Phase 3 Tracking document⁸ and to provide a summary of the results via the Piloting Events Reports folder⁹. On top of that, all results of events and possible future events to engage in piloting were also discussed at bi-weekly communication meetings. In this way, all results were communicated and documented. A discussion and analysis of the results from the user feedback will be detailed in deliverable D2.4 and D5.3.

⁷<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Lq3Bhd7et8RLJyRSBAEPgwXSY68GIX4EwHJVy3xQJhY/edit#gid=0>

⁸ [Mobius Pilot Phase 3 tracking.xlsx](#)

⁹<https://eurecatcloud.sharepoint.com/sites/MOBIUS/Shared%20Documents/Forms/AllItems.aspx?FolderCTID=0x012000B494CBCA387C2546B477238DC47F7472&id=%2Fsites%2FMOBIUS%2FShared%20Documents%2FWP5%20M%C3%B6bius%20experimental%20productions%2FPilot%20Phase%203a%2FPiloting%20event%20reports&viewid=4a73bb09%2D891d%2D48df%2D884c%2D0a2759ba9d20>

3. Möbius Creator's Toolkit Prototype

The Möbius Creator Toolkit is the main integrated application that enables prosumers to create Möbius books and manage the books they have previously created.

Because it is built as a web-application, the Möbius Creator Toolkit is compatible with all operating systems. In fact, since it uses responsive technologies, the application can work well on various devices and screen resolutions (including tables and mobiles).

The current version of the prototype is accessible at: <https://mobius-creator.in-two.com/login>

3.1. Workflow updates

Based on the feedback received from pilots (as described in Chapter 2), IN2 has improved the previous application release both in terms of ease of use, functionality, and integration.

User Management

The user management and login component are responsible for both the Möbius Player and the Creator Toolkit. In the final release minor bugs discovered during the piloting were addressed, including one related to the use of special characters in the Password chosen (which resulted in the user not being able to register the account). The final process to sign-up and login for an account is now extensively tested and working flawlessly.

The login dialog box features a white background with a light gray border. At the top, the word "Login" is centered in a large, bold, black font. Below it, the text "Sign in to your MOBIUS-CREATOR account" is centered in a smaller, gray font. The form contains two input fields: "Username or Email *" with a person icon on the left, and "Password *" with a lock icon on the left and an eye icon on the right. A gray "Login" button with a right-pointing arrow icon is positioned below the password field. At the bottom, there are two links: "No account yet? Let's create one" and "Forgot password? Reset", both with right-pointing arrow icons.

Figure 3: The login dialog

Usability improvements and user onboarding

First of all, the terminology used in the application has been adapted, to reflect better the vocabulary used by prosumers and remove confusion which was sometimes reported in the initial user feedback. Moreover, improvements in the user interface have focused on hiding the internal mechanics of the applications, hiding from the user the underlying complexity whenever possible. This led to a simplification of forms, with additional options being available to the user only when content is being edited (but not at creation time).

Onboarding refers to the process of integrating and familiarizing new users with a particular software or platform. It typically involves guiding users through initial setup, introducing key features, providing tutorials, and facilitating a smooth transition to ensure users can effectively and efficiently use the software from the outset. Effective onboarding enhances user experience, reduces learning curves, and promotes user retention.

Because initial user feedback has indicated that the application can prove to be difficult to get started by first-time users, IN2 worked on providing an onboarding functionality using contextual hints that can guide the user through the workflow of creating a new Möbius book. The hints are provided at the top of the page, having a distinct colour to distinguish them from the rest of the application and include the actual clickable buttons so that the user can immediately get started.

Figure 4: Example of user hints provided under the Books menu

Once the user is familiar with the application, the hints for onboarding can be removed by adjusting a setting in the user profile.

Figure 5: User profile (focus on hints toggle)

Workflow for creating Mobius books

The general workflow for creating a Mobius book has been streamlined and also extended to integrate additional functionality. The whole process is top-down driven, with the user creating a book as a container for the underlying content. The book is composed of chapters and each chapter by paragraph blocks, intermixed with audio-visual content. Audio and narration can also be added at book and chapter level.

If a user chooses to create a new book, an initial set of information must be provided, most importantly a title and a short summary of the book. The specification of the “genre” has also been introduced in order to facilitate better sorting and exploration functionality in the Player. Moreover, the user can create a contribution campaign and ask other prosumers to provide content, defining the start date and end date of the campaign.

The screenshot shows a form titled "ADD BOOK" with the following fields:

- Title ***: A text input field with a placeholder "Write a title for your book. Max length 255 characters." and a character count of "0 / 255".
- Genre**: A text input field with a placeholder "Write comma-separated genre for your book Max length 255 characters." and a character count of "0 / 255".
- Short summary**: A text input field with a placeholder "Write a short summary for your book. Max length 1000 characters." and a character count of "0 / 1000".
- Contribution campaign start date**: A date picker field with a placeholder "You can ask for contributions using a book-specific contribution campaign link. Select here the date on which your contribution campaign will start." and a calendar icon.
- Contribution campaign end date**: A date picker field with a placeholder "You can ask for contributions using a book-specific contribution campaign link. Select here the date on which your contribution campaign will end." and a calendar icon.

At the bottom of the form, there are two buttons: "Save" (with a floppy disk icon) and "Close".

Figure 6: Form for creating a new book

Once a user has created a book, this is seen under the “All Books” section. The “Book card” design has been improved and includes apart from the meta info (title, description, update

time) also actionable buttons to edit existing chapters or directly create a new chapter in the book. The book can be edited and previewed, and if a contribution campaign is active, get the link to share. All these options are easily accessible from the menu; hovering over the icons will show you a short hint about what each of those is about.

Figure 7: Overview of created book

Overall, the workflow for creating and assigning chapters has been improved. If the “Book card” the user selects to “Add chapter”, then a form to create the chapter is opened and upon saving, the chapter is assigned to the book and the user can add content to the chapter.

The screenshot shows a form titled "Chapter" for adding a new chapter. It has two main input fields: "Chapter Title (required)" and "Tagline (optional)". The "Chapter Title" field has a placeholder "Set a title for your Chapter" and a note "Write your Chapter's title. Max length 80 characters." The "Tagline" field has a placeholder "Add a tagline" and a note "Write your Chapter's tagline. Max length 255 characters." At the bottom of the form are "Save" and "Cancel" buttons.

Figure 8: Form to add a new Chapter

If a contribution campaign is active, this is displayed under the info about the Chapters of the book. It specifies if the campaign is ongoing, what is the start and end date, and if ongoing an additional button to reach the contribution page is shown. The page that allows prosumers to contribute content has a simple but functional design, allowing prosumers to easily upload any type of content in bulk. The uploaded content is visible only to the user that has created the campaign.

Figure 9: Web link for a contribution campaign

All prosumers can contribute content to a campaign, but before they are able to do so they need to have an account with Möbius and they need to confirm that the contribution is publicly available content and/or is the contributor's own content and she/he has permission to store and share it and give permission for it to be stored and shared via the MOBIUS tools and its users.

Register

Before you can contribute content, you have to register below.

Expires Mon, 27 Nov 2023 23:23 UTC

By registering you will be able to see the data you have contributed to MOBIUS and ask us to withdraw material if you have changed your mind or exercise any other right related to GDPR. We do not hold or use your personal data for any other use.

Username

Required. Min length 4. This field is part of the url of your account.

Email

Required. Make sure that this is valid email, so you are not missing out.

Password

Required. Min length 8. Can contain any character except spaces.

I confirm that this contribution is publicly available content and/or is my own content and I have permission to store and share it and give permission for it to be stored and shared via the MOBIUS tools and its users.

Create Account

Already have an account? Login to MOBIUS-CREATOR and import this content.

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Figure 10: Intermediate step for a user who is not logged-in to contribute to a campaign

Once the content is uploaded, the prosumer can first review the contributions. The contributor has to manually toggle the “Share” button in order to make his contribution visible to the campaign creator.

Figure 11: Sharing contributed content with a campaign owner

An important integration in the current version of the Creator application has been the integration of the Montreal Forced Aligner¹⁰, an open-source project that facilitates the alignment of text and audio narration, and the integration of the Spatial Audio Composer, which provides the needed functionality for positioning 3D elements into spatial 3D audio. This integration is described in Section 3.2 in more detail. Each chapter of a book can have its own set of audio files attached to it. On the end-user interface, the functionality is under the "Audio" tab of the Edit Chapter menu. The different available audio files are presented to the user. A manual process has to be undertaken in order to define what type of audio it represents (i.e., narration, sound effects, music, mix).

¹⁰ <https://montreal-forced-aligner.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

Figure 12: Adjusting the audio elements of a chapter – selecting relevant audio files

If the selected audio file, is of type “narration”, the user can select to align the audio with the text available. This triggers an asynchronous process on the backend which tries to accomplish the alignment of the text and the audio. Because the process is asynchronous, the user can leave the page and carry out other actions until the alignment process is completed.

Figure 13: Adjusting the audio elements of a chapter – aligning text and audio narration

Once the narration audio and the text are aligned, the user can open the Spatial Audio Composer (“Create 3D Audio” button) and place the audio sources in a 3D space. The Spatial Audio Composer opens up in full screen.

Möbius Spatializer!

You'll probably want to use **Chrome, Opera or Edge** to run it. Firefox and Safari currently don't work.

Pan the Sound (drag the Dot)!

Sound Clips (drag to a track!):

Add Clip (Upload Audio File): No file chosen

Global Parameters:

Play/Stop Distance Attenuation

Text and Arrangement

Track
sfx_1
sfx_2
music_1
music_2

Mehmet stood up and, with a deep breath, let his gaze wander above the strait. He looked at his right and saw the dark, vigorous Black Sea, immense in its unending power. All the copious amounts of water it received from the tributaries and the sky created the relentless tides of the

Figure 14: Adjusting the audio elements of a chapter – saving in 3D space the audio

After saving and going back to the Book Audio menu, 6 additional audio files are then available for use: vox, sfx, music, voxmusic, sfxmusic, full mix.

Book Chapters Cover Image **Audio**

Select from below which audio files are part of this Book. *It is recommended to select at least an audio which contains the narration of your book text.* Using this narration file you can then align the text of your book with the audio and create different versions of 3D audio for your book.

- Bosporus by G SFX + MUSIC | AUDIO_SFX_MUSIC Clear
- Bosporus by G VOX + MUSIC | AUDIO_VOX_MUSIC Clear
- Bosporus by G FULL MIX | AUDIO_FULL_MIX Clear
- Bosporus by G MUSIC | AUDIO_MUSIC Clear
- Bosporus by G SFX | AUDIO_SFX Clear
- Bosporus by G VOX | AUDIO_VOX Clear
- Bosporus by G - Narration | AUDIO_NARRATION Clear

Ready | Clear |

Figure 15: Adjusting the audio elements of a chapter – overview of the audio files

The process for using chapters and collections of media into chapters has also been simplified, in that these are now separate. The top bar displays only “Books”, “Media” and “Content”. So, for creating a media collection to include in a chapter, the user can go to “Media”, create a collection and add content to it (e.g., images). Then they can get directly from the main list of collections, the needed embedded code to add in a text.

Figure 16: Chapter or media collection view

Adding content to “Content” has also been streamlined. The interface (shown below) has in the final version only 3 options: adding a paragraph, a call to action or media (any type).

Figure 17: Content upload form

3.2. Architecture and integration updates

In order to integrate the spatial audio composer (SAC) into the final Möbius creator's toolkit prototype, we have decided to include the interface of the SAC using an HTML-iframe. For this, the source code from the original prototype of D4.3 was to be stripped down to accommodate the new server integration.

The Spatial Audio Composer functions have both an audio alignment to text as well as positioning different audio elements in spatial 3D audio over binaural audio. The user uploads a narration file matching to a part of the text to be analysed and aligned. Because this process can take some time to complete, the user may close the browser window and return at a later time to check on the status of the analysis. After the alignment is complete, the user can open the Spatial Audio Composer to see the alignment result and listen to the narration with the text highlighted in real-time, so that it can be verified that the alignment was done correctly.

To facilitate the UX of aligning the audio of a narrator to the written text, an asynchronous process using a Docker container was built. The original server-side source code of the SAC was modified to run in a Docker container in the background. As such, the user can close the Möbius creator's toolkit webapp and return later to check if the analysis of the alignment is complete. Once the container has finished its process, a flag will be set for the user to see that the SAC can be loaded for the respective section of text. This way, the user can now instantly load the SAC with the aligned narration without having to apply the analysis each time, which, depending on the length of the text, can be a lengthy process.

The user can then upload audio files containing music and effects, which can be placed and aligned to any word in the text as shown in the UI. The user can then place these sounds at different positions via 3D binaural audio using the provided 3D UI element. Once complete, the user can click export to produce the final ePub version of the book.

4. Möbius Player Prototype

The Möbius Player has also been improved based on the feedback received from the piloting actions. It can be accessed at: <https://mobius-player.in-two.com/>

The homepage of the player keeps the same broad structure as in the previous version, providing a list of books in three main sections: a) Recommendations (personalised recommendations based on user preferences), b) Best seller (curated list of books by the app admin) and c) New releases (as an entry point for exploring what is available). If a user is logged in, a link to access the Creator tool is prominently displayed next to the profile picture. Similar to the Creator, hints for facilitating user onboarding are displayed at the top of each page and can be turned on and off from the profile page.

Explore - This is the home page of the Player. It provides a list of books in three main sections: a) Recommended for you, b) Best seller and c) New releases as an entry point for exploring what is available. Please note that only the book *Bosporus*, which is part of "The Influence of the Blue" has content that will allow you to experience the Möbius tools. Clicking on the star icon below each book, adds this book to your Library enabling you easier and faster access to it.

You can disable hints by editing your [profile preferences](#)

Recommended for you

Best Seller

New releases

Figure 18: Möbius player homepage for logged-in user

The page of the user profile has also been improved, especially with regards to the look and feel. The profile from the Creator is kept in sync with that from the Player.

MÖBIUS Books Library Activity Möbius Creator

Profile - This is your personal profile page. You can add or update your personal information, avatar, social media links, preferences and interests below. You can disable hints by editing your profile preferences.

Personal Information

This information might be displayed publicly so be careful what you share.

First name: Alexandru Last name: Stan

Email address: a@in-two.com Username: astan

About: R&D manager at IN2

Write a few sentences about yourself. Max length 160 characters. Remaining 142 chars.

Photo: [Change](#)

Website: <https://in-two.com> Twitter: [@AlexandruStan](https://twitter.com/AlexandruStan)

Instagram: [instagram.com/](https://www.instagram.com/) Facebook: [facebook.com/](https://www.facebook.com/)

Preferences

Choose your preferences

User Interface

Hints and Help
See all hints and help information on every page.

Personalise

Choose min 3 topics you like, we will give your more often content that relates to them.

Action and Adventure Art and Photography Contemporary Fiction Dystopian Fantasy

Fiction Food and Drink Historical Fiction Horror Mystery Romance

Science Fiction Thriller and Suspense

Finish → Back to Books

About FAQ Imprint

Figure 19: User profile

If the user is logged in, bookmarking of interesting books and commenting on books can be done. Moreover, the “Library” and “Activity” menus are being shown to logged-in users. The “Library” provides a list of books that have been starred by bookmarking them.

Clicking on the star icon below each book, will toggle (remove/add) this book from the “Library” of the user. The activity page shows the user the activity across all books in the Player. The user can easily see stars and comments for books that other readers added and explore further books they might enjoy.

Figure 20: View of the Library

The short view of the books has been updated to include more meta information (e.g., number of chapters, number of words). While previously only one audio file was supported alongside the text, the final version allows for several audio tracks to be played (music, sound effects, narration, or a combination of those). The user can stop or resume the audio tracks anytime.

Fantasy into Möbius

Winner of the Möbius Fantasy open call

by @astan | 8 minutes ago | Chapters: 1 | Words: 1057

 Play Audio

 Read Book

Figure 23: Book overview

The additional media information which the user can encounter in the text and access by clicking the Möbius icon, is no longer breaking the flow of the story. Instead, in the final version, the media is displayed as a continuation of the story, in the form of a pop-up.

5. Conclusion

In this document, the final steps to a fully functional prototype are described. User feedback studies were used to acquire potential features, which were sorted, prioritized and implemented. The identified features along with those that were already described in deliverable D5.3 individually have been successfully integrated into a coherent, web-based tool.